

Future Directions and Design Strategies for Polyoxometalate-Soft Matter Composite Materials

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Abstract: Molecular metal oxides, or polyoxometalates (POMs) offer unrivalled properties in areas ranging from catalysis and energy conversion through to molecular electronics, biomimetics and theranostics. While POMs are ubiquitous metal oxide model systems studied in most areas of chemistry and materials science, their technological deployment is often hampered by their molecular nature, as this leads to increased degradation, leaching and loss of reactivity, particularly when harsh applications, such as water electrolysis, thermal catalysis or highly basic/acidic reaction solutions are targeted. Therefore, immobilization of POMs on heterogeneous substrates has recently become a central theme in POM research. While early studies focused mainly on metal oxide and semiconductor supports, more recently, POM integration in soft matter matrices including polymers, conductive polymers, hydrogels and stimuli-responsive matrices have led to breakthroughs in multifunctional composite design.

This Progress Report will summarize the recent pioneering studies in this emerging field, highlight current challenges which need to be overcome to allow a more widespread technological deployment and provide the authors' view of some of the most promising future directions of the research field. In addition, we provide an unprecedented summary of the correlations between structure (on the molecular, nano- and microscale) and resulting reactivity, so that materials design beyond empirical studies can be further developed. We believe that this timely Progress Report will serve as a focal point to further develop the field, as well as point of reference for newcomers in the area of knowledge-driven bottom up materials design. Given this broad range of interest groups, we believe that *Advanced Functional Materials* is the ideal journal for this Progress Report.

1. Introduction

The combination of hard and soft matter – often thought of as inorganic and organic components, can yield functional composites with unique and otherwise inaccessible properties. Prime examples are found in Nature, where biomineralization forms bones in vertebrates or shells in molluscs. These composites combine mechanical strength with flexibility and offer structural stabilization and protection. These materials are composed of hard inorganic components, *e.g.* calcium carbonate, CaCO_3 or hydroxy apatite, $\text{Ca}_5[\text{OH}(\text{PO}_4)_3]$, and polymeric soft matter, *e.g.* collagens, which are combined to give new structures and unique function.^[1] In this Perspective, we will explore the combination of polymeric soft matter matrices with molecular metal oxides – polyoxometalates (POMs) – as a unique class of composites where structure, reactivity and function can be controlled on the molecular level, while giving macroscopic materials suitable for technological device integration, *e.g.* as membranes, films or gels.

1.1. The relevance of embedding molecular metal oxide species in soft matter.^[2,3]

Soft matter: The 21st century may rightfully be called the era of soft matter. The term “soft matter” was officially introduced in science by Pierre-Gilles de Gennes in his noble prize lecture in 1991.^[4] In contrast to hard matter, which is characterized by structural rigidity and strong (*e.g.* covalent or ionic interactions), soft matter possesses properties in between solids and liquids and is dominated by weaker, intermolecular interactions (*e.g.* dipolar or hydrogen bonding interactions) between the constituents. These systems are flexible and are responsive to external forces or stimuli. Further, “soft matter” features structuring on different length scales from nano- to micrometers, and the macroscopic behavior of soft matter is dictated by non-covalent, intermolecular interactions. Based on these characteristics, polymers, colloids, surfactants, organic and metal-organic films, liquid crystals, vesicles, biological object etc, are all examples of soft matter.^[5]

Among those, polymers represent a thriving and promising field which was established about 100 years ago by Staudinger.^[6] Later on, the discovery of living anionic polymerization in 1956^[7] and stereoregular polyolefins^[8] provided facile access to materials on a large scale. The interest in polymers as industrial materials was also driven by the invention of 3D printing in the 1980s, which provided access to hierarchically complex architectures, which were not achievable by conventional manufacturing technologies.^[2] In addition, the discovery of controlled polymerization techniques in the 1990s significantly increased the portfolio of accessible materials and functionalities.^[9] Another breakthrough in soft matter was the development of block copolymers which chemically link two or more polymer-chains into one compound, resulting in unusual structure and new function.^[10] In the last three decades the focus of polymer chemistry has shifted to stimuli-responsive or “smart” materials, which adapt to environmental changes by changes of structure or reactivity, enabling application in sensing, drug delivery, self-healing coatings, or tunable catalyst supports.^{[11][12]}

With the development of polymer chemistry, the interest to incorporate inorganic materials into polymers also emerged. Significant influence on development of such polymer-inorganic nanocomposites can be ascribed to the discovery of “chimie douce” in 1980s.^[13] With that, sol-gel-based approaches were established as an alternative to traditional high-temperature “shake and bake” chemistry and the resulting (composite) materials were characterized by extended organic–inorganic interfaces. The combination complementary properties of organic (soft) and inorganic (hard) matter opened up the way for materials with unique, sometimes even synergistic, characteristics.^[14] This led to extensive applications in fields like sensing, bio-imaging, photovoltaics, or in catalysis.^[3]

Figure 1: Historic overview of POM-polymer hybrid materials

Hard and soft matter composites: In the classical approach of catalytically active hybrid materials often a catalyst is grafted or anchored on the surface of an inorganic support (e.g. silica, titania, or alumina). The obtained heterogeneous catalyst typically shows high thermal stability, good performance and can be easily recycled.^[15] The reverse approach, where inorganic catalytic species are attached to a (structured) polymeric surface is less common, presumably due to a (perceived) lower stability of soft matter. However, polymer-supported catalysts open avenues which would not be possible with classical inorganic supports. Soft matter offers superior local control of the catalyst environment, e.g. by careful selection of building block for nanostructured polymer matrices. This can even enable approaches where polymers model the well-defined reaction-spaces of biological systems, e.g. enzymes.^[16] This allows control over morphology, chain folding, and the presence of functional groups at the molecular level and could even result in the formation of artificial enzymes.^[17] In addition, selection of stimuli responsive block allows to obtain smart catalytic materials in which the catalytic function can be controlled by external stimuli like changes in pH, temperature, or irradiation with light of a specific wavelength.^[18] The selectivity and activity of the material can also be tuned by variation of local polarity in the vicinity of the catalytic center.^[19] Currently, plenty of different inorganic materials were used for formation of polymer-inorganic composites, however in this review we focus only on polyoxometalate-polymer hybrids.

Polyoxometalates: POMs are ideal molecular components for integration into soft matter matrices, based on their structural versatility combined with an enormous range of applications: POMs are molecular metal-oxide anions, typically based on early transition metals (group 5, 6) in their highest oxidation states.^[20–22] POMs self-assemble spontaneously in solution by oligo-condensation reactions of oxometalate precursors (e.g. MoO_4^{2-} , WO_4^{2-}), sometimes in the presence of templating anions (e.g. halides, oxo-anions, etc.).^[23] POMs contain between 2 and 368 metal centres, are typically in the 1 – 5 nm size range and can feature several tens of negative charges.^[20–22] POM structure formation is difficult to predict, but can be influenced by secondary reaction parameters including solvent, pH-value, temperature, pressure and others.^[20] To-date, POM chemistry is dominated by W-, Mo- and V-based POMs, as these metal feature the ideal combination of high positive charge, suitable ionic radius and availability of empty d-orbitals to stabilize terminal oxo ligands by d-p π -bonding.^[20–22]

Over the last decades, advances in synthesis, characterization and mechanistic understanding have led to breakthroughs in POM applications ranging from (photo-)catalysis,^[24,25] energy conversion/storage,^[26] molecular magnetism and electronics^[27,28] through to bio-medicine,^[29–31] and artificial enzymes.^[30] Of particular interest over the last decade was the development of POMs covalently functionalized with organic groups to merge the fields of metal oxide and organic chemistry.^[32,33] In addition, the redox-activity of POMs renders them ideal components for charge-transfer and storage as well as (photo-)redox catalysis. In addition, surface protonation of POMs makes them intriguing acid catalysts.^[34] Metal functionalization of the POM cluster shell can be used to

further tune structure and reactivity.^[23,35,36] The most commonly used POM structure types are summarized in Fig. 2. Due to their molecular nature, POMs can easily be dissolved in various solvents, and solubility can be controlled by the type of counter-cation used.^[37] This feature makes POMs amenable for solution-processing, so that incorporation in a wide variety of organic, bio-organic and inorganic heterogeneous matrices (including polymers, proteins, solid oxides) becomes possible.^[38]

Figure 2. Prototype POM structures discussed in this report.

2. POM-soft matter embedding strategies

2.1. General deposition strategies

Two general approaches can be identified for the integration of POMs in soft matter matrices, that is the use of covalent (so-called Class I hybrids) or non-covalent linkages (so-called Class II hybrids).^[14] For POMs, non-covalent materials integration is synthetically more straight-forward. Thus, early studies focused in Class II POM-polymer hybrids. In 1983, Parmon et al. reported the first example of electrostatic POM integration in soft matter. The group immobilized $H_4[SiW_{12}O_{40}]$ or $H_3[PW_{12}O_{40}]$ on a poly(2-vinyl pyridine) anion exchange resin. However, the resulting composite did not show the proposed light-driven hydrogen evolution activity, possibly due to the absence of mobile protons in close proximity to the POM.^[39] Nevertheless, also examples with increased catalytic activity after immobilization are known, such as shown by Wang and co-workers who prepared $H_3[PW_{12}O_{40}]$ -based polymer bearing different degree of polymerization. Interestingly the dependency of catalytic activity of tetrahydrothiophene oxidation in the presence of H_2O_2 versus size of polymer was detected. The Polymer bearing 10 repeating units demonstrate the highest catalytic activity that was found to be 2.5 times higher than unsupported POM cluster.^[40]

Class I hybrids: In class I POM-polymer hybrids, the components are linked covalently, and are therefore considered more durable. However, due to synthetic challenges in covalently linking POM and polymer, this materials class is still in its infancy. First, organo-functionalized POMs suitable for covalent linkage to polymers are required, which limits the number of suitable candidates, mainly to Keggin, Dawson, Anderson and Lindqvist ion derivatives.^[32,33] These species can be modified by organic anchoring groups, typically using multidentate tethering groups such as phosphonate or silyl moieties. (Fig.3 A).^[33] However, note that these linkages can be chemically labile and result in a lower overall stability of the cluster. In addition, given the large number of polymers available, no generalized

strategies for POM-to-polymer attachment exist, and each system needs to be carefully tuned for optimum POM covalent attachment.^[41] We also note that often, covalent modification of polymers with POMs significantly affects the resulting composite properties, often leading to decreased solubility in general,^[42] which causes challenges for materials processing and application. However, when developed successfully, this approach gives access to new materials with synergistic and often unexpected properties. The covalently linked POM-polymer hybrid materials can be separated into five main classes, based on the location of the POM (Fig 2C). The POM can be incorporated (a) into the polymer side chain, (b) into the polymer backbone, (c) as chain end group, (so called head – tail hybrids), (d) as crosslinking agent, (e) in dendrimeric structures.

Based on the synthetic method, covalently linked POM-polymer hybrids can be produced directly by polymerization of POM-modified monomers or by post-polymerization modification. The first covalently attached POM-polymer hybrid was obtained by P. Judeinstein in 1992 by direct polymerization of organofunctionalized Keggin-type POMs $[(RSi)_2SiW_{11}O_{40}]^{4-}$ (R = vinyl, allyl, methacryl, styryl) using free radical polymerization. The reactivity of the POM-containing monomer increased in the order vinyl \ll allyl $<$ methacryl $<$ styryl, suggesting that the proximity of the cluster to the polymerizable group decreases the polymerization rate. Due to the presence of two polymerizable groups in one POM cluster, a mixture of branched and linear polymers was obtained, where the POM was located along the polymer backbone.^[43]

POM-polymer hybrids where the POM is incorporated along the backbone are usually synthesized by step-growth polymerizations, *e.g.* polyaddition and polycondensation. One particularly interesting example of polyaddition was reported by Song and colleagues who performed photoinduced [2+2] cycloaddition of bis-coumarin modified Anderson POMs (Fig.3, a). The success of polymerization can be visually monitored by change of the colour of polymer from colourless to red due to increase of chromophore system. Upon 90 min of irradiation polymers with molar masses of 337 kDa and a dispersity of 1.60 could be obtained.^[44] Also, the use of CLICK chemistry (Cu-catalyzed alkyne-azide coupling) has been reported by Cronin and co-workers to access POM-oligomers based on suitably functionalized Anderson-POM (Fig.3, b).^[45] Here, the authors first design di-POM-based “monomers” featuring terminal amine groups at either end of the molecule. Chain growth was then enabled by functionalizing the terminal groups with alkyne moieties which could then undergo further CLICK-linkage. This route can be repeated, leading to well-defined Mn-Anderson hybrids ranging from dimers to pentamers. Despite unprecedented control over the polymerization process, the proposed strategy is still limited due to the difficulties in synthesizing unsymmetrically functionalized POMs.

Figure 3: A) and B) represents the two main strategies of POM modification through the formation of Lacunary POM structure (A) and by ligand exchange (B). C) represents five main classes of POM-polymer hybrids based on their chain configuration: (a) side-chain, (b) backbone, (c) head-tail PPHs (d), crosslinked and (e) dendrimers. The red symbols represent the POM clusters. Selected examples of formation POM-polymer hybrids where the POM is located in the polymer backbone that was achieved by a) photoinduced [2+2] cycloaddition and b) alkyne-azide coupling polymerizations. Reproduced from references 13-14 with permission.

The integration of POMs into polymer sidechains has for example been achieved by ring-opening polymerization of norbornene monomers modified with Dawson-POMs. The polymerization occurred nearly quantitatively and resulted in POM-polymer hybrids where $[H_4P_2V_3W_{15}O_{62}]^{5-}$ POM clusters are attached to well-defined polynorbornene backbones (Fig 5a). Molar masses up to 600 kDa and a low dispersity (PDI = 1.2) were reported, which corresponds to 100 POM-norbornene repeating units. The resulting composite showed catalytic activity for the oxidation of tetrahydrothiophene and could also be processed into thin films.^[40] The same Dawson-type POM has also been used for the formation of head to tail type POM-polymer hybrids by ATRP (Fig.4b). Here the macroinitiator was synthesized at first through the ligand exchange pathway between POM and bromofunctionalized tris-(hydroxymethyl)methane. This macroinitiator was then used in polymerization reactions towards polystyrene-based head-to-tail hybrids with molar masses up to 119 kDa. Exchange of lipophilic NBu_4^+ cation to hydrophilic H^+ resulted in the formation of giant amphiphiles with hydrophilic POM headgroups and long hydrophobic tails, forming vesicles via self-assembly in aqueous media.^[46] RAFT polymerization techniques have been used to access /poly(*N,N*-diethylacrylamide) composites using trithiocarbonate-functionalized Dawson-type phosphotungstates as chain transfer agent and AIBN as initiator. Here, chain transfer agent (CTA) synthesis was performed through the formation of a lacunary POM with the next tin modification followed by azide-alkyne coupling (Fig. 4c). This led to head to tail hybrid polymers with molecular weights in the range of 10 to 100 kDa and dispersities < 1.5.

The covalent attachment of POMs to pre-formed dendrimers has been possible by post-polymerization modification. For example, $[H_4P_2V_3W_{15}O_{62}]^{5-}$ Dawson POMs have been directly attached

to dendrimers featuring terminal tris(hydroxymethyl) groups through transesterification. The material obtained was used as a catalyst for the tetrahydrothiophene oxidation using *t*BuOOH or H₂O₂ as oxidant. Catalyst recycling and reuse by precipitation and filtration-recovery has also been demonstrated.^[47] Also, for Keggin-POMs, dendrimer attachment has been achieved by reaction of dendrimer-based amino groups with tin chloride modified POM clusters.^[48]

Figure 4. Selected examples for the utilization of controlled polymerization techniques a) ROP, b) ATRP and c) RAFT for the formation of covalently linked POM-polymer hybrids. Reproduced from references 48-50 with permission

Class II hybrids: The simplicity of electrostatic attachment of anionic POMs to cationic polymers has made it the most used approach for POM-in-polymer integration, and various polymers have been used, including quaternized poly(vinylpyridine), polyimidazole, polyaniline, protonated polylysine, polypyrrole, poly(vinylchloride), polyethylene-*block*-polydimethyl aminoethyl methacrylate, or polystyrene-*block*-poly(2-dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate).^[49] Despite the facile composite preparation, non-covalent attachment can often lead to POM leakage under operation, and particularly pH changes. Especially in case of electrostatic attachment, drastic changes in pH can lead to weakening of the interaction and removal of POM from the polymer matrix. Nevertheless, reversible attachment upon changes in pH could be potentially used for metal recovery and polymer recycling. In addition, electrostatic attachment is the method of choice for the formation of hierarchically structured 1D-3D POM-polymer hybrid materials. Particularly, when block-copolymers with chemically different “blocks” (e.g. a hydrophilic and a hydrophobic block) are used, then access to POM-functionalized hierarchical structures including micelles, vesicles, thin films, membranes, fibres, or porous solids becomes possible (Figure 5). In addition to direct mixing of POM and polymer during the preparation, electrostatic POM-anchoring is also possible as a post-functionalization method of the pre-formed polymer. So far the direct mixing of POM with polymer is rather difficult as in this case all component should be well soluble in one solvent.^[50] More often the attachment of POM is realized due to the electrostatic attachment of POM to polymers bearing an amino function, that also could be introduced in the commercial polymer network like poly(vinylidene difluoride) (PVDF) by plasma treatment.^[51]

Figure 5. Overview of 1D, 2D and 3D POM-polymer structures obtained using to block-copolymer self-assembly.

2.2. Challenges in characterizing molecular species embedded in heterogeneous matrices. Key (*in situ/operando*) techniques to assess reactivity, stability, and structural integrity.

The structural analysis of POM integrity within the soft matter matrix is most often performed using surface spectroscopic and microscopic techniques. In the following chapter, key techniques are presented, and their relevance is demonstrated by appropriate literature examples.

Fourier-transform and attenuated total reflectance infrared spectroscopy (FT-/ATR-IR) are suitable solid-state methods to study materials such as powders, (hydro)gels^[52], films^[53], membranes,^[54] *etc.*, and to verify POM presence and integrity in a polymer matrix^[55,56] POMs exhibit intense, characteristic metal-oxygen vibrational modes in the fingerprint region of $1000\text{--}500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which are highly sensitive to structural changes, degradation or interactions with the environment. Hence, IR-spectroscopy can be used, e.g. to assess POM stability or leaching in reactivity studies by analysis of POM-characteristic signals in the fingerprint region $< 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.^[57–59] In addition, POM-polymer interactions can be experimentally studied, including hydrogen bonding,^[56] π -stacking^[60], electrostatic^[52,53] ionic^[56] and covalent attachment^[61,62] by analysis of the specific vibrational features.^[56,60,63] IR spectroscopy (in combination with other methods) also allows to track the progress of a reaction by evaluating changes in vibrational intensities, as demonstrated by Judenstein et al. for a (POM-methacrylate) polymerization reaction, where the intensity decrease of the polymer-based C=C-vibration is used as spectroscopic probe.^[64]

Raman spectroscopy: Raman spectroscopy is a vibrational spectroscopy method to characterize POM-polymer composites which offers higher signal resolution compared with conventional IR spectroscopy. However, it typically operates at high excitation laser power, which can cause damage to sensitive samples. In one example, Aguado-Ureta et al.^[65] used confocal Raman microscopy (CRM) to access depth profiles/cross sections of composite films containing POMs. The study highlighted that POM-identification within the films is possible at high spatial resolution, enabling the observation of homogeneous POM distribution. In another example, Jacob, Travaš-Sejdić, Streb and co-workers used *operando* Raman-spectro-electrochemistry to explore reversible redox-cycling of POM-conductive polymer composites.^[66] Yang et al. used *in situ* Raman-spectroscopy to assess structural changes, degradation and substrate binding in a mesoporous POM-soft matter hybrid.^[57]

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS): XPS is a surface sensitive (top few nm) technique to quantify the elemental composition of solids under ultra-high vacuum. The technique can also be used to study POM or polymer surface-processes including structure changes, degradation, diffusion or leaching.^[67] In addition to the detection of characteristic binding energies and the assignment of metal oxidation states, changes in signal intensity ratios can be used to gain insights into chemical changes before and after specific reactions.^[58,68]

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy: Solution and solid-state NMR spectroscopy methods can be used to probe the structural integrity of POMs and their interaction with polymers. In one example, Yamada et al. studied a Keggin-phosphotungstate embedded in a copolymer matrix.^[69] The authors used ³¹P-NMR to verify the cluster integrity and to explore the reactivity loss during recycling. Sullivan et al.^[61] used the solid-state method Cross-Polarization Magic Angle Spinning (CP-MAS) ¹³C-NMR to examine the presence of covalent bonds between polymer-anchored 1,3,5-benzenetricarboxamide linkers and polyoxovanadate clusters. The presence and integrity of the vanadate cluster itself was confirmed by solid-state MAS-⁵¹V-NMR and solution ⁵¹V-NMR.

Ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) absorption and emission spectroscopies can be used to probe the presence and reactivity of POMs in soft matter.^[59] In one example, Bazzan et al.^[70] designed a polymer containing Anderson-type POM and organic spiropyran. The materials showed strong solid-state photochromism which was tuned by the POM loading amount. In another example, Wei et al.^[71] reported a pH-responsive POM-soft matter hydrogel unusual, POM-dependent luminescence properties.

Elemental Analysis (CHN, ICP-OES): The determination of metals and most non-metals in composite materials by elemental analysis (EA) such as CHN analysis and inductively coupled plasma optical/atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES/AES) allow validation of elemental compositions,^[72] determine POM- and organic contents,^[58] and assess POM stability and leaching resistance.^[58]

SEM & EDX: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) provides nanometer-resolution information of the morphology^[52], micro- and nanostructure of POM-soft matter systems. When combined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), structural and elemental information can be obtained, e.g. to study POM incorporation and distribution in soft matter matrices.^[51,58] Bonchio et al. used SEM-EDX to investigate the surface and cross-sectional morphology of a photocatalytically active POM-polymer membrane, and provide information on membrane changes during catalysis.^[73] Streb, Schacher and colleagues reported light-driven hydrogen evolving nanoporous block copolymer membranes functionalized with a molecular photosensitizer ($[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$) and a HER-active catalyst ($[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$).^[74] SEM-EDX was used to explore the distribution of the molecular components on the membrane surface.

Figure 6. A and B: SEM in top view (A) and cross section (B) of non-functionalized membrane. Inset A: photograph of the functionalized membrane showing the characteristic colour of the immobilized molecular species. C and D: DX elemental mapping (Mo/Ru) mapping of functionalized membrane.

High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) provides down-to atomic resolution analysis of thin samples. Due to the large difference in electron density, HR-TEM is particularly suitable for studying POM distributions in organic soft matter. In one example, Breu, Kamperman and co-workers showed that different nanostructures (micelles, networks, vesicles) can be accessed in POM (H3PM12O40) / PB-*b*-PDMEAMA hybrids, depending on the POM-to-polymer ratio. Bsp.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM): AFM studies can be performed under ambient conditions on non-pre-treated (*e.g.* dried) samples. This gives access to surface topology and roughness of POM-polymer hybrids. For example, Aguado-Ureta et al.^[65] used AFM to show that POMs of different size feature distinct distributions at polymer interfaces.

Surface / surface area examinations (WCA & BET): POM immobilization often significantly affects the polymer surface microenvironment and thus its (catalytic) activity and selectivity. Water contact angle measurements (WCA) are useful to follow changes in the surface hydrophilicity and to validate successful POM functionalization. In two examples, Fontananova et al.^[51] and Lopez et al.^[68] studied the effect of plasma-chemical POM-modifications and ageing of membrane surfaces using WCA experiments. POM immobilization on polymers usually increases its surface area, which can be assessed by BET-physisorption measurements.^{[75],[76]} In addition, this technique allows an examination of pore size distributions of the composite material.^[77]

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) can be used to quantify the POM-content in a POM-polymer hybrid by determining the amount of combustible components.^[56] In addition, TGA provides information on the thermal stability^[53] and degradation temperature^[62] of the samples studied. **Dynamic scanning calorimetry (DSC)** can further be used to identify melting/solidification behaviour^[60] and glass-transitions^[72] in POM-soft matter composites, *e.g.* hydrogels.^[52]

Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectroscopy provides insights into the electronic states of POMs embedded in soft matter. In one example, Ghali et al.^[78] followed the catalytic performance and oxidative re-generation of POMs when embedded in a polymer matrix using EPR spectroscopy.

Electrochemical analyses are ideal tools to study the redox-activity of POMs embedded in redox-active or conducting polymers. Voltametric-, bulk electrolysis and related studies can provide critical

information on the accessible oxidation states, changes in reversibility and electron storage/transfer capabilities of the materials studied.^[62,64,72,79]

2.3 Computational Studies on Polyoxometalates-soft matter composites.

In the last two decades, the number of publications dedicated to computational studies of POMs has increased steadily. The rise on computational power alongside the appearance of novel theoretical methods has made possible to target transition metal compounds with high accuracy.^[80] Recent reviews^[81,82] have covered some of the applications of theory to POMs. However, the number of computational studies addressing POM-soft matter composites is far below that focus on computed properties of POMs. Here, we shall review computational studies of POM-soft matter composites, first pointing to the challenges associated to model POMs.

Computational methods. Even though theory has been able to provide qualitative and quantitative descriptions of the properties of isolated POMs, this path has been far from straightforward and hindered by the many limitations of the available methods. Atomistic simulations can employ quantum mechanical (QM) methods (see bottom of Figure 7), either based on ab initio wave function or density functional theory^[83] (DFT). Whereas wave function methods quickly become unfeasible as the size of the molecular system increases, DFT has a better trade-off between cost and accuracy and is therefore most popular. DFT studies of POMs until 2012 can be found in the excellent review from López et al.^[82] Recent examples, where DFT has aided the interpretation of experimental data or predicted POM properties include the calculation of redox potentials^[84–86] X-ray spectra,^[87] reaction mechanisms^[86,88–90] and non-linear optical (NLO) properties.^[91–93]

When it comes to study the interaction of POMs and soft-matter, the larger dimensionality of the global system makes necessary to involve classical approximations. Most methods in this category involve to carry out molecular dynamics (MD) simulations based on parametrized force fields –a field as also known as molecular mechanics (MM). In this fashion, atoms are considered classical balls that follow Newtons equation in time. To recover QM effects and thus improve accuracy, hybrid QM/MM methods^[15] divide the system in (at least) two regions, a small one that is treated quantum mechanically with high accuracy and the rest that is described with a suitable force field. The different flavors of QM/MM methods depend on how the interaction between the QM and MM regions is described. The computational cost of QM/MM is roughly as expensive as that of the chosen QM method, and thus combined with MD, propagation time scales are shorter than those achieved with MD (see Figure 7). When the system is much larger that computational feasibility of all-atom MD allows or propagations in the μ s-ms are targeted, coarse-grained^[96] modelling can reduce the number of degrees of freedom by defining a group of atoms as a so-called bead. Despite their lower resolution as compared with all-atom simulations, combined with MD exhibit a computational speedup of the order of N^2 , with N the number of particles.^[97] To reach larger spatial and time scales, at the meso- or macroscale, supra coarse-grained MD strategies includes one or more molecular units in one bead (see top of Figure 7). Furthermore, static information on the posing or interaction modes between POMs and macromolecular systems can be addressed by means of molecular docking.^[98]

Figure 7. A general hierarchical scheme of different modeling approaches, including approximate time-scales and system sizes that can be studied with each method. Reproduced with permission from reference ^[99] (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Modelling POM geometries: For a start, before any molecular properties can be calculated one requires an accurate prediction of the equilibrium geometry. If the system is flexible one needs to sample and rank energetically all accessible conformers. Unlike for main group element containing molecules, conformational energy benchmarks for transition metals are scarce and they lack the inclusion of POMs in their datasets.^[100,101] It is worth noting that in recent times there are also great efforts devoted to develop new functionals that allow to compute routinely several hundreds of atoms, while conserving the accuracy of more computationally demanding counterparts.^[102–106] Regarding flexibility, Jahn-Teller (JT) effects and redox isomerism should also be considered when describing the conformational landscape of POMs. For example, the DFT studies of López et.al.^[107] found that intrinsic geometrical distortions present in molybdates are due to pseudo JT distortions. Likewise, Nishimoto et.al.^[108] attributed JT distortions as the driving force for the molecular and electronic structure changes during super-reduction of a α -Keggin POM cluster. Very recently, some of us^[109] showed that the position of JT axis influences the local reactivity in a MnV based POM,^[110] which stands as a synthetic mimetic of the oxygen evolving complex in natural photosynthesis.

Modelling POM electronic properties: As POMs are composed of transition metals, they inherit their associated challenges. If calculating relative energies of different spin states can be a difficult task in a transition metal complex, to do so in a POM is considerably more challenging as the many metals increase the number of oxidation and spin states. Ideally, such problems are best treated with QM methods^[108] able to deal with the multi-configurational situations that most likely such structures incur. However, multi-configurational QM methods are computationally very demanding and applications to POMs are scarce.^[111,112] Alternatively, the relative stability of high and low-spin states is often calculated with the more cheaper broken-symmetry DFT approach.^[113,114] In this framework

the low-spin manifold is accessed by a variational self-consistent-field optimization of a mono-configurational wave function, where the sign of the spin-density of an atomic center is inverted to represent a lower symmetry state compared to the high-spin state. One example of low-spin states calculated in this fashion is inside the computed redox potentials of a MnV based POM^[86] but many more exist. Broken-symmetry DFT has also been employed to calculate magnetic properties of POMs.^[115,116]

Modelling POMs embedded in polymers

Due to their large size, high conformational flexibility, and often amorphous shapes, the choice of a computational technique to model polymers is far from trivial.^[117] Particularly, for the study of POMs-polymers integration, all-atom MD simulations and coarse-grain MD approaches are by far the most popular choices.

Dendrimers is one family of polymers whose integration with POMs has been computationally studied. The composite POMs@dendrimers systems are termed artificial dendrizymes,^[118,119] as they are intended to have certain structural resemblance with natural metalloproteins and to be applied as enhanced catalysts. The early study by Volkmer et al.^[119] on a heteropolytungstate cluster encapsulated in a shell of dendritically branching surfactants laid the foundations for later applications of all-atom MD simulations on POMs embedded in dendrimers.^[120,121] Their study was mostly qualitative in nature, giving insights into the packing arrangement of dendrons over the anionic metal cluster. More recently, several studies combining theory and experiment have been carried out on Perfluorosulfonic acid polymers (PFSA) doped with heteropoly acids (HPAs), which is a subset family of POMs.^[122–125] PFSA are able to form proton exchange membranes, which upon doping with HPAs should see an increase in the proton conductivity capabilities. Liu et al.^[122] combined experiment and theory to study the PFSA membranes doped with H₃PW₁₂O₄₀ and H₄SiW₁₂O₄₀ HPAs. All atom MD simulations assisted the understanding of the observed enhanced proton conducting capabilities of the membranes, by addressing the solvent distribution morphology. From their calculations, they concluded that this enhance conductivity was due to a trapping mechanism of solvent water molecules around the HPAs that forms a hydrogen-bonding network.^[122] A study by the same group^[123] followed a very similar modelling protocol to provide additional information regarding the balance between the loading of HPAs and the resulting conductivity. Relying solely on computer simulations, Akbari et al.^[124] studied the doping of Nafion® 117 with H₃PW₁₂O₄₀, H₅IW₆O₂₄, H₉AlW₆O₂₄, and H₂W₆O₁₉. They applied MD simulations coupled with quantum mechanically derived proton hopping^[126] to investigate the hydrogen bond network and structural diffusion of protons. This method allows to compute rate constants of proton hop between water molecules and to detect decreased activation energies in the proton migration between two adjacent water molecules when the POMs are integrated in the Nafion® 117. The same authors also employed all-atom MD simulations to investigate in more detail the creation of a change in the water network triggered by POMs through a detailed percolation analysis.^[125]

Computational simulations of other mechanisms, such as co-assembly of POMs and polymers, requires access to time-scales much longer than those accessed by atomistic MD methods, e.g. using coarse-grained MD.^[117] In this manner, Li et al.^[55] showed the time evolution of a supramolecular star polymer with a Keggin-type POM cluster core ([CoW₁₂O₄₀]) and block-copolymers. The system was composed of a supramolecular star co-polymer with the POM as a core and a solution of a block-copolymer. Their simulations showed the time evolution of the system going from the formation of toroidal micelles (Figure 8, left) to their assembly into cylindrical micelles (Figure 8, right), which nicely agreed with

measured AFM images. Very recently, coarse-grained MD was also used to simulate the self-assembly mechanism of POM nanoparticles decorated with mobile polymer ligands (i.e. via electrostatic interactions),^[127] providing designing rules for tailored self-assembly into lamellar, cylindrical, and spherical structures.

Figure 8 Left: (a-c) course-grained MD snapshots of the micelles. (d-f) AFM images of intermediate states during the formation of toroids. Right: (a) AFM image of the coexisting shapes of the micelles, (b) snapshot from the simulated early stage formation of the toroidal micelle, (c) snapshot from the simulated evolution of the toroidal micelle into cylinder shape.^[55] Copyright 2021 American Chemical Society.

Complementary to the methods above, it is also possible to take truncated models of POM-polymers structures that then allow for QM calculations. For example, De Luca et al.,^[128] in a joint experimental and theoretical work, constructed a model system composed of: i) the Keggin POM $[\text{PMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^{3-}$, ii) one and three acryloyloxyundecyltrimethyl ammonium bromide surfactant tails, and iii) 36 explicit water molecules, that was analyzed with DFT calculations, through a rather elaborated protocol. The non-covalent interaction energies among this Keggin POM, bromide atoms, and the surfactant and solvation energies were computed to provide insights into the bromide ion exchange process led by the POM. In another study, NLO properties were calculated in a POM cluster with attached polymeric chains as a pendant.^[129] By creating a model system of one attached polymer chain with a maximum of six repeating units, time-dependent DFT calculations were performed to elucidate the structure/property relationship that leads to tunable NLO properties.

Modelling POMs in miscellaneous soft-matter environments

Although there are less examples, computational chemistry has been also used to study the integration of POMs in lipid bilayer membranes and surfactants or to analyze self-aggregation processes. For example, a study from Carr et al.^[130] made use of coarse-grained MD to propose a route for spontaneous self-assembly of a POM nanocapsule into a phospholipid membrane. Klaiber et al.^[131] fabricated a novel surfactant by self-assembly of a Keggin-type polyoxometalate functionalized with anthraquinone via a π -conjugated chain. The supramolecular composite showed promising capabilities as an electron reservoir and frontier molecular orbitals were computed at the DFT level of theory to understand the electron confinement properties. Galiano et al.^[132] integrated a surfactant encapsulated POM into a polymerizable bicontinuous microemulsion to create a novel smart material for wastewater treatment. By using DFT QM/MM calculations, non-covalent binding energies between the POM and the surfactant tails were evaluated in order to analyze the stability of the supramolecular system.^[132] Segado Centellas et al.^[133] prepared soft nanostructured materials through aggregation of

dumbbell-like POM units joint by hybrid organic-inorganic linkers and DFT calculations were used to analyze the electronic configuration of the metal centers at the linkers; additional all-atom MD simulations provided further insights into the assembly mechanism.

3. Application-driven POM-soft matter composite design

3.1. Solar and electrochemical energy conversion, catalysis

POM-polymer composites are key materials for energy conversion and storage, and have been used in batteries, supercapacitors, fuel cells and electrocatalysis. The field has been reviewed recently, and is therefore not discussed in detail here.^[134–136]

3.2. Stimuli-responsive Materials and Applications in Sensors

As described above, polyoxometalates are versatile compounds and of interest for various applications. It can be beneficial to enhance selectivity or tune solubility by combining POMs with stimuli-responsive materials such as polymers or biomolecules. In that way, a variety of different triggers can be used to activate specific properties of the POM that are required in different environments. The most common triggers for responsive materials are pH, heat, light and electricity. Due to their versatility POMs can be responsive to all these triggers under suitable circumstances. With these different triggers applications of responsive POM/organic hybrid systems in various fields such as theranostics,^[137] sensors,^[134] catalysis^[138] or redox systems^[139] are possible. Decisive for the application of POMs in different soft matter matrices are the controlled accessibility of the POM and at the same time the sensible enhancement of the POM's properties.

For many applications the embedding of POMs in organic thin films is a suitable method. This provides a high stability of the resulting systems and functional polymers enhance the properties of the POMs. Different thin film formation methods are employed, including Langmuir-Blodgett deposition, spin-coating, as well as layer-by-layer (LbL) methods, where cationic and anionic layers are deposited in an alternating fashion.^[140] These deposition methods are ideally suited for the deposition of POMs and subsequent application in sensing and stimuli-responsive materials.^[140] When integrated into electrochemical devices, redox-active POMs can be coupled to external electrical stimuli to trigger changes of their physico-chemical properties, such as their redox-states. In one example, Volkmer *et al.* used LbL assembly to fabricate thin films containing the polycation poly(allylamine hydrochloride) (PAH) as positively charged layer and anionic layers composed of the polyanion poly(styrenesulfonate) (PSS) and the Preyssler-heteropolytungstate anion $[\text{Eu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{P}_5\text{W}_{30}\text{O}_{110}]^{12-}$.^[141] Films with switchable electrochromism, short response times and high cyclic stability were reported

Similar concepts have been used for the assembly of POM-based sensors, which often utilize the POM redox-activity to detect gases or toxins. In one example, Kurth *et al.* use LbL assembly to fabricate a POM-based sensor for nitrogen monoxide. To this end, alternating layers of the polyelectrolytes PSS and PAH were deposited on an ITO electrode, followed by the alternating adsorption of the cobalt containing Dawson based POM $[\text{Co}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2(\text{P}_2\text{W}_{15}\text{O}_{56})_2]^{16-}$ and PAH. The resulting multilayer assembly shows selective gas permeability and sensing selectivity. The deposition of a PSS/PAH/PSS surface layer was used to prevent anion (e.g. nitrite / nitrate) diffusion into the film, so as to prevent unwanted redox-reaction of the POM with these species. High sensitivity for NO detection (down to 1 nM) was reported.^[142]

POMs can also be utilized in sensors by the embedding in thin films of conductive organic polymers. This allows substrates to access redox-active POMs which can be directly electrically addressed via the conductive polymer.^[134] McCormac *et al.* prepared an electrochemical sensor for the detection of hydrogen peroxide based on a polypyrrole film with transition metal-substituted Dawson-POMs as dopant anions. These films were directly deposited on a glassy carbon electrode by electropolymerization from solutions containing pyrrole and the respective POM.^[143]

Another approach to POM-based sensing materials is the use of lanthanide-functionalized POMs. These compounds can show excellent photoluminescent properties, such as long decay times and intense and sharp emission bands.^[144] Li *et al.* used the photoluminescent Preyssler anion $[\text{EuP}_5\text{W}_{30}\text{O}_{110}]^{12-}$ together with PAH for LbL film assembly.^[145] Building on this principle, Yao *et al.* immobilized Europium-containing polyoxometalates in agarose nanocomposite films to create photoluminescent sensors for gaseous acids and bases. Based on pH-dependent on/off switching of the europium-based red luminescence.^[146]

A related concept for the development of luminescent POM-polymer hybrids is the immobilization of POMs in hydrogels. This can lead to sensors with response mechanisms based on pH, light or humidity. Wan *et al.* used an ABA triblock copolymer and a $[\text{Dy}(\text{W}_5\text{O}_{18})_2]^{9-}$ POM for the reversible formation of a supramolecular hybrid hydrogel. The DMAEMA units of the hydrophilic poly(DMAEMA)₃₅-*b*-PEO₂₃₀-*b*-(DMAEMA)₃₅ triblock copolymer can be protonated. This has been used for the electrostatic co-assembly of protonated DMAEMA with anionic POMs. Notably, the emission behaviour of the system changed significantly upon gelation, so that applications as smart, pH-sensitive materials can be envisaged.^[71]

A similar approach has been established for carbon dioxide detection in solution using core-shell nanostructures based on PEO₁₁₄-*b*-PDMAEMA₁₆ diblock copolymers electrostatically functionalized with $[\text{Dy}(\text{W}_5\text{O}_{18})_2]^{9-}$ POM. Also, here the DMAEMA units of the block copolymer are protonated during changes in pH. In this case, the pH change is induced by the acidic reaction of CO₂ in water. Due to the missing third block in the block copolymer, however, the mechanism for the change of fluorescence is different. The block copolymer and the POM do not form hydrogels but complexes. When the pH is decreased by dissolved CO₂ the charged DMAEMA units assemble around the negatively charged POMs. This leads again to a change of the fluorescence color from weakly green to white. When the solution is then purged with inert gases the CO₂ is removed from the solution, which leads to the disassembly of the complexes and the sensor can be used again.^[147]

3.3 Biomedical Applications

POMs have been employed in a range of biomedical settings including antiviral, antimicrobial and anticancer applications.^[31,148] However, for *in vivo* applications it is crucial to mediate their toxicity and increase the selectivity as well as their mode of action. Linking POMs to biologically inspired soft matter matrices is a method of choice to achieve these goals.

One approach has been reported by Wang *et al.* The group combined POMs with lipids to access Another interesting option is the combination of POMs with lipids to generate liposome-encapsulated $[\text{SiW}_{11}\text{TiO}_{40}]^{6-}$. In these systems, the POMs were encapsulated spherical lipid-bilayer vesicles ($d = 15 - 60$ nm), resulting in a significant drop in toxicity during *in vivo* anticancer studies. Further *in vitro* studies showed improved cell-membrane penetration and enhanced antitumor activity and stability in comparison to the pure POM.^[149] Similar effects have also been reported when POMs were covalently attached to lipids. Liu *et al.* functionalized a Preyssler-POM with a long-chain organoalkoxysilane lipid.

The amphiphilic POM hybrids spontaneously assemble into vesicles and exhibit significantly increased antitumor activity in comparison to the pure POMs. According to the authors, this difference is due to the improved cell-membrane binding and cell uptake of the functionalized POM.^[150]

A similar approach is the encapsulation of POM in chitosan, a polysaccharide copolymer of β -(1,4)-2-acetamido-D-glucose and β -(1,4)-2-amino-D-glucose. Chitosan is known to enhance *in vivo* drug delivery whilst reducing undesired side-effects.^[37] These benefits have been explored in the encapsulation of POMs in chitosan matrixes, targeting bio-medical applications.^[38] In one example, Nair *et al.* used a POM/chitosan hybrids as potential anti-cancer treatments. The group designed stable, monodisperse hybrid nanoparticles with a diameter of *ca.* 200 nm by encapsulating the europium POM $[\text{Cs}\langle\text{Eu}_6\text{As}_6\text{W}_{63}\text{O}_{218}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{14}(\text{OH})_4]^{25-}$ were prepared by a simple ionotropic gelation method. The hybrid was tested against a range of cancer cell-lines *in vitro* and showed a slow and sustained POM release, so that significantly lower doses of the hybrid were required (based in IC_{50} values) compared with the pure POM reference.^[151]

A different approach to anti-tumor activity of POM-polymer hybrids has been reported by Wang, Chen and co-workers. The group used semiconducting polymer brushes and POM clusters which aggregated specifically to larger in the low pH, reducing microenvironment of a tumor. This led to enhanced retention of the particles in the tumor. Further, chemical reduction of the Mo-based POM resulted in enhanced NIR light absorption, enabling efficient use in hyperthermia-inducing photothermal therapy.^[152]

3.4. Molecular electronics

The anchoring of electronically or magnetically active POMs^[28,153,154] in functional polymers holds great promise for the design of unique composites, *e.g.* for molecular electronics, quantum computing or spintronics. To-date, most studies in the field have focused on the deposition of POMs on metal or semiconductor surfaces, while POM-polymer composites have received little attention. This could in part be due to the challenging fabrication and processing of POM-polymer composites, particularly when sub-nanometer accuracy in the positioning of the POMs is required. For molecular electronic, this precision is needed, as electronic and magnetic interactions between neighbouring POMs have major impact on their performance, *e.g.* in the context of the loss of information due to quantum decoherence effects.^[28]

In a pioneering example, Mallah, Wernsdorfer, Mialane and co-workers embedded the single molecule magnet (SMM) POM $[(\text{FeW}_9\text{O}_{34})_2\text{Fe}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{10-}$ ($= [\text{Fe}_6\text{W}_{18}]$) into a gelatine biopolymer. Magnetic analyses showed similar behaviour between the pure POM compound, and the POM-gelatine-composite, highlighting that the sensitive magnetic properties of the POM were not affected by the (diamagnetic) gelatine matrix.

Redox-active POMs can also be used as reactive sites in molecular junctions, *i.e.* systems where molecules act as charge-transfer sites between two metal electrodes. D. Velessiotis and co-workers^[155,156] demonstrated that POM-polymer composites can be used as active materials in molecular junctions. The group fabricated a PMMA- $[\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]$ composite and

provided first insights into the electronic transport properties of the system. In particular, the authors report that POM-concentration as well as electrode geometry are two key factors for electron transport. Two distinct transport mechanisms (tunnelling vs hopping) were reported depending on the electrode distances.

The design of a POM- polymer composites for nonvolatile, rewritable multilevel memories was reported by Zhang and co-workers.^[157] The authors used Anderson-POMs covalently linked into the backbone of a PMMA polymer as active compound. The material showed three distinct redox states with long retention times. Resetting the material to enable re-writing was possible by careful choice of the redox potentials employed.

Other POM-based applications in molecular electronics and related fields have recently been reviewed by Chen, Dong and co-workers.^[158], and Zhou, A. L. Roy, S.-T. Han and co-workers.^[159]

In summary, the use of POMs with controllable spin and/or redox states combined with the flexibility, processability and scalability of soft-matter polymers holds great promises to realize nanoscale devices for molecular electronics. Key for the further development is understanding the role of POM-distribution, composite structure from nano- to microscale as well as engineering robust and functional polymers which contribute to the device performance.

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